
Improving Human Resource Capacity to Achieve Quality Public Services in the Education Sector

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ABSTRACT

Improving the quality of public services in the education sector is closely related to the capacity of human resources within public organizations. Sub-district education coordination units play a strategic role in supervising, coordinating, and facilitating educational services, yet their performance is often constrained by disparities in educational background, limited access to training, weak mentoring systems, and issues of work discipline. This study aims to analyze human resource capacity development and its contribution to improving the quality of public services at the Regional Education Coordinator (Korwil) of Cepu District, Blora Regency. A qualitative descriptive approach was employed, with data collected through in-depth interviews, direct observation, and document analysis. Informants were selected purposively and consisted of supervisory assistants, administrative staff, teachers, and education personnel who interact directly with the Korwil, totaling ten informants. Data analysis followed an interactive model involving data condensation, data display, and conclusion drawing, supported by methodological triangulation. The findings indicate that human resource capacity development has been implemented through formal and informal education, job training, promotion and job rotation, mental development, work discipline, and performance evaluation. However, these efforts remain uneven, particularly between supervisors and administrative staff, due to constraints related to educational qualifications, training opportunities, employee motivation, age factors, and welfare conditions. The study concludes that strengthening human resource capacity through inclusive training policies, structured mentoring systems, continuous performance evaluation, and improved employee welfare is essential to achieving sustainable improvements in the quality of public services in the education sector.

KEYWORDS: Human Resource Capacity, Public Service Quality, Education Sector, Local Government, Qualitative Study

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1. INTRODUCTION

Public services are a concrete manifestation of the state's presence in fulfilling the basic rights of citizens. In the context of modern governance, the quality of public services is not only measured by the fulfillment of administrative procedures but also by the level of effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, and responsiveness of the apparatus to the needs of the community (Qin et al., 2025; Sedarmayanti, 2013). Therefore, bureaucratic reforms carried out by the government, both at the central and regional levels, consistently place improving the quality of public services as a strategic agenda in realizing good governance.

One of the determining factors for the success of bureaucratic reform and improving the quality of public services is the capacity of the human resources (HR) of the apparatus. A professional, competent, adaptive-to-change, and strongly public service-oriented civil service is a key prerequisite for the delivery of quality services (Anugrah et al., 2021; Dwiyanto, 2021; Hardiyansyah, 2018). In the digital age and with the ever-evolving dynamics of policy, improving HR capacity is no longer optional but an urgent necessity for public organizations to be able to respond to increasingly complex public demands (Mutiarin et al., 2024; Poljašević et al., 2025; Wibowo, 2018).

In the education sector, the quality of public services has very strategic implications because it is directly related to long-term human resource development. The Regional Coordinator for Education in Cepu District, Blora Regency, has an important role in carrying out supervisory, guidance, coordination, and facilitation functions for educational units. The implementation of these functions

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requires officials who have technical competence, administrative skills, and communication skills, as well as a strong work ethic and professionalism (Askim et al., 2025; Ismi et al., 2025; Krpálek et al., 2021)

In addition to administrative and managerial aspects, the education sector also faces cross-sectoral social issues, one of which is stunting. Stunting is a condition of growth failure in children due to chronic malnutrition that occurs in the first 1,000 days of life and has a significant impact on cognitive development, learning abilities, and the quality of human resources in the future (Rahman, 2025; Sideropoulos et al., 2025). In this context, education officials are not only required to carry out administrative tasks but also play a role in supporting cross-sectoral

However, empirical conditions in the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit show that the capacity building of officials has not been optimal. Although most supervisors have met the minimum educational qualification of a bachelor's degree, administrative staff are still dominated by high school/equivalent graduates. Normatively, these qualifications do meet the job requirements, but the sharp difference in educational backgrounds has created a competency gap between employees (Hasibuan, 2017). This gap has implications for variations in performance quality, particularly in information technology mastery, modern administration management, and public service communication skills.

This problem is exacerbated by the lack of continuous training and competency development. Existing training has not been able to reach all employees equally, while the process of knowledge transfer from senior employees to other employees has not been well structured. As a result, mastery of information technology, digital administration skills, and the ability to adapt to policy changes are still relatively limited (Alvarenga et al., 2020; David et al., 2024; Mathis et al., 2016; Mondy & Martocchio, 2015). In fact, digital transformation in public services requires civil servants who are not only tech-savvy but also able to use technology effectively to improve service quality (OECD, 2021).

In addition to technical competence, work culture issues are also a serious challenge. The continued existence of undisciplined behavior, low initiative, and dependence on colleagues in completing tasks shows that the professionalism of civil servants has not been fully internalized. The lack of continuous training and performance coaching makes it difficult for employees to adapt to the dynamics of the organization and the demands of increasingly fast and transparent services (Dessler, 2019; Wibowo, 2018)

From the perspective of personnel management, the suboptimal system of human resource management and development has hampered the improvement of civil servant capacity. Employees with high competence and experience have not been strategically empowered as mentors or guides for other employees. In fact, the implementation of mentoring and coaching systems has been proven to accelerate the improvement of human resource capacity and strengthen the learning culture in public organizations (Armstrong, 2017; Ganesh et al., 2015; Mcilongo & Strydom, 2021; Umar et al., 2025). On the other hand, the emergence of employees entering retirement without being accompanied by a process of regeneration and regeneration of human resources has the potential to create labor shortages and disrupt the continuity of public services.

Employee welfare factors cannot be ignored either. The economic conditions of some employees who have to seek additional work due to financial pressures have an impact on their focus, energy, and work motivation. This directly or indirectly affects the quality of services provided to the community (Amin & Yusra, 2021; Ampong, 2024; Soetrisno, 2016). Thus, improving human resource capacity is not only related to education and training but must also be supported by adequate welfare.

Overall, these various issues emphasize that improving the human resource capacity of the Cepu District Education Coordination Office is an urgent and strategic need. The quality of human resources is a key factor in the success of public organizations in providing effective, responsive, and community-oriented services (Anugrah et al., 2021; Dwiyanto, 2021; Xatse & Naong, 2025). In line with Wirawan's opinion in Puryana & Okta (2022), the quality of human resources includes physical and non-physical abilities—such as skills, thinking abilities, attitudes, and work ethic—which directly determine the quality of public services.

Based on Hasibuan's theory of human resource capacity building, the development of the civil service must be carried out through education, training, and continuous guidance and supported by an adequate personnel management and welfare system. However, the reality in the field shows limitations in technology mastery, access to continuing education, a lack of administrative training, and weak regeneration and mentoring systems. The findings of this study are consistent with previous studies, which show that the quality of human resources and employee competency development significantly affect the quality of public services across various local government contexts. Research in Palu City found that human resource performance affects the quality of public services (Saleh et al., 2024), while another study emphasizes the need for human resource development strategies for excellent service (Sofiyah et al., 2024), and a survey of district governments shows the importance of developing the capacity of bureaucrats in the production of public services (Gunawan et al., 2025).

Based on this description, there is a gap between the ideal demands for increasing the capacity of the apparatus' human resources and the empirical conditions that occur in the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit, Blora Regency. Therefore, this research is important to examine in more depth the "Improving Human Resource Capacity to Achieve Quality Public Services in the Education Sector" in order to provide theoretical contributions and practical recommendations for the development of public services in the education sector.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research design with a descriptive approach to examine human resource capacity development and its contribution to improving public service quality in the education sector. A qualitative approach is appropriate for understanding organizational processes, institutional practices, and the experiences of public service actors in depth, particularly in relation to capacity building and service delivery (Creswell, 2018; Miles et al., 2014). A qualitative approach was chosen because this study seeks to explore the perceptions, experiences, and interpretations of education administrators and staff regarding human resource capacity development, including training, competence, work culture, and organizational support (Moleong, 2012; Sugiyono, 2022).

The research was conducted at the Regional Coordinator (Korwil) Education Sector, Cepu District, Blora Regency, which was purposively selected due to its strategic role in supervising, coordinating, and facilitating educational services at the sub-district level. This institution functions as an intermediary between schools, local government, and the community, making it a relevant setting for examining human resource capacity development. Informants were selected using purposive sampling based on their roles, experience, and relevance to the research objectives. The informants consisted of the Head of the Regional Coordinator (Korwil), supervisory assistants, office administrators of the Korwil, as well as teachers and education personnel who interact directly with the Korwil in the delivery of public services, with a total of ten informants. These informants were chosen because they possess firsthand knowledge of capacity-building practices, administrative processes, and service quality in the education sector.

Data were collected through in-depth semi-structured interviews, direct observation, and document analysis. Interviews were conducted face-to-face to capture informants' perceptions and experiences regarding training, competence, work discipline, and organizational support. Observation was used to understand daily administrative practices and service interactions, while documents such as policy regulations, activity reports, and administrative records were analyzed to support and triangulate primary data. Data analysis followed the interactive model proposed by Miles et al. (2014), consisting of data condensation, data display, and conclusion drawing. To ensure the trustworthiness of the findings, methodological triangulation was applied by comparing data from different informants, data collection techniques, and documentary sources.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Improvement of Formal and Informal Education

Improvements in formal and informal education are important indicators in efforts to increase human resource capacity in the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit in Blora Regency. Based on interview results, efforts to improve education are considered a relevant strategy for increasing employee competence and the quality of public services.

The Supervisory Assistant for Regional Education Unit 3 stated that improving education has a direct impact on HR competencies, especially for employees who do not yet have a bachelor's degree. However, he also emphasized the importance of time management so that improving education does not have a negative impact on public services:

"Efforts to improve education are very appropriate, as they will increase human resource competency. Considering that employees in the Cepu Regional Coordination Unit do not yet fully have bachelor's degrees, it is hoped that improving education will increase human resource competency so that the quality of public services can also be improved. However, improving education by attending face-to-face lectures, if time is not managed properly, will disrupt and even reduce the quality of public services. Therefore, time must be managed effectively so that educational improvement (attending lectures) does not interfere with the quality of public services."

This statement was reinforced by the Supervisory Assistant for Regional Education Unit 1, who said that although most supervisors already have bachelor's degrees, administrative staff still need to improve their educational qualifications so that public services can run more optimally:

"Employees within the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit do have bachelor's degrees, especially the supervisors, but some of the administrative staff only have high school or associate's degrees, so they still need to improve their qualifications to a bachelor's degree level in order to provide the best possible public services. However, our colleagues always provide the best service."

From the perspective of office administrators, the interview results show a desire to improve education, but they face structural and personal obstacles. One office administrator said that time and cost constraints are the main obstacles to continuing education:

"In the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit, only one administrative staff member has a bachelor's degree, while the rest, including myself, have only a high school diploma. We would like to continue our education to a higher level, but this is hindered by the fact that college classes are held during working hours and the cost of tuition is certainly not cheap. If only the government allocated a budget for employee education, such as scholarships for employees or civil servants, it would certainly ease our burden in pursuing further education."

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In addition to time and cost constraints, the issue of degree linearity also arises. Another office administrator stated that even though they already have a bachelor's degree, it cannot be used for adjustment because it is not linear and was obtained before being appointed as a civil servant:

“Some of us administrative staff already have bachelor's degrees, but most do not. I also have a bachelor's degree, but it is not linear, and I obtained it before being appointed as a civil servant. We hope that in the future, we will be given flexibility in adjusting our degrees or, if they must be linear, we will be given flexibility, such as through courses outside of working hours. Most importantly, we hope for scholarships from the government for civil servants, because without scholarships, it will be burdensome to pay for them.”

Meanwhile, other office administrators emphasized that improving human resource capacity should not only be done through formal education but also non-formal education, especially in mastering information technology:

“Improving human resource capacity must be done, especially by enhancing skills in technology such as the internet and computers. To achieve this, if courses are required, it will also burden our finances. We hope that the government will provide scholarships or free training for employees so that they can master technology, especially since we are no longer young.”

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be interpreted that the improvement of formal and informal education in the Cepu District Education Coordinator's office has been carried out, especially for supervisors. However, for office administrators, improving education still faces various obstacles, such as limited time, costs, and diploma adjustment policies. Nevertheless, employees continue to show their commitment to providing optimal public services.

Table 1. List of Employment History and Education of the Regional Coordinator for Education in Cepu District

No.	Name / Position	Employment History	Formal Education	Non-Formal Education
1	Sri Rahayu Suswatiningsih, S.Pd	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 1986 2. School Supervisor, 2012	1. SPG (Teacher Training School), 1984 2. Bachelor's Degree (S1), 2023	–
2	Aris Munandar S.Pd, M.Pd	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 1993 2. School Principal, 2012 3. School Supervisor, 2013	1. Diploma (D2), 1992 2. Bachelor's Degree (S1), 2002 3. Master's Degree (S2), 2021	–
3	Eko Setyo Budi, S.Pd, SD	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 2009 2. School Principal, 2023 3. School Supervisor, 2025	1. Diploma (D2), 2024 2. Bachelor's Degree (S1), 2009	–
4	Sartono, S.Pd	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 2009	1. Bachelor's Degree (S1), 2005	–
5	Karsono, S.Pd	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 2014 2. Office Administration Staff, 2021	1. Bachelor's Degree (S1), 2004	–
6	Sugeng Prasetyo, A.Ma	1. Civil Servant Teacher (CPNS), 2009 2. Office Administration Staff, 2024	1. Diploma (D2), 2005	–
7	Sinto	1. Security Staff, 2009 2. Office Administration Staff, 2024	1. Senior High School (SMA), 1997	–
8	Masrukin	1. Security Staff, 2006 2. Office Administration Staff, 2021	1. Primary School (SD), 1995 2. Junior High School (SMP), 1998 3. Senior High School (SMA – Paket C), 2017	–
9	Sukiran	1. Security Staff, 2007 2. Office Administration Staff, 2024	1. Primary School (SD), 1983 2. Junior High School (SMP), 1989 3. Senior High School (SMA – Paket C), 2005	–

Source: Official Regional Coordinator Document (2025)

2) Job Training

Job training and education are essential indicators for improving human resource capacity in the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit in Blora Regency. The training aims to improve employees' knowledge, skills, and professional attitudes in carrying out their public service duties.

Based on interviews with the Head of the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit, who is also the Supervisory Assistant for Regional Education Unit 2, the implementation of training is considered a mandatory requirement for employees. However, the level of awareness among employees regarding participation in training varies:

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“To improve the competence of employees in the Cepu Coordination Unit, training, seminars, and similar activities are necessary. These are mandatory for all employees. However, in the Cepu District Education Coordination Region, there are those who are consciously willing to improve their competence. But there are also many who are unwilling for various reasons.”

This statement shows that even though the training policy exists, its implementation has not been fully optimized due to differences in motivation among employees. This is reinforced by the statement of an office administrator working in the finance department, who said that the intensity of training is still lacking:

“It is better to have training and an even distribution of employees so that optimal service can be achieved, but until now there is still a lack of training for employees.”

On the other hand, the Supervisory Assistant for Regional Education Unit 4 assessed that the equal distribution of training opportunities in the Cepu Regional Office was quite good, especially for supervisors, and that the knowledge gained could be utilized and shared with colleagues:

“Equal distribution in the delivery of employee training is very necessary for improving the quality of employees in their services. The opportunity for equal distribution of employee training in the Cepu Regional Coordination Unit is good, so that the knowledge gained can be passed on and the skills possessed can be utilized in accordance with the competencies appropriate to the field.”

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be interpreted that job training in the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit is not yet evenly distributed among positions. Supervisors have greater opportunities to participate in training compared to office administrative staff. In addition to opportunity factors, employees' personal motivation also influences their participation in training. This condition indicates that improving human resource capacity through job training still needs to be supported by equitable policies and strengthened employee motivation so that the results of training truly have an impact on improving the quality of public services.

Figure 1. Intensity of Education and Training Opportunities Based on Position

Source: Data processed by researchers (2025)

3) Promotion and Job Rotation

Promotion and job rotation are important strategies in human resource management, especially for placing employees according to their capacity, competence, and experience. In the Cepu District Education Coordinator's office, promotion and job rotation have been implemented as an effort to equalize service quality.

Based on interviews with the Head of the Cepu District Education Coordination Unit, promotions and job rotations are carried out to avoid service gaps and encourage knowledge transfer between employees:

“Promotions and job rotations are essential to ensure that service quality is consistent across all sub-units, thereby avoiding service gaps within sub-units and ensuring equal service provision. In the Cepu District Education Coordination Region, we try to place several employees who have more abilities and are willing to share their knowledge with their colleagues. However, sometimes there are also employees who have less human resource capacity, such as a lack of motivation to learn, which becomes a slight

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problem in service delivery. Nevertheless, because consultation and coordination are always carried out well with superiors and colleagues, and they continue to try to learn.”

This view is in line with the opinion of the Supervisory Assistant for Regional Education Unit 1, who emphasized that promotion and job rotation based on human resource capacity greatly affect the achievement of organizational performance:

“Promotion and job rotation based on human resource capacity are very important for the achievement of performance targets. The Cepu District Education Coordination Unit has employees with good human resource capacity. They have good IT skills and collaborate well with each other. However, there are still some employees who have not maximized their capacity and still need motivation and encouragement from their surroundings. With employee rotation, it is hoped that employees with less ability can learn from those who are more capable.”

From the perspective of office administrators, job promotions are highly desired, but are often constrained by age and educational qualifications:

“Job promotions and rotations need to be carried out in the civil service, especially job promotions. With sufficient length of service and the required rank/position, job promotions can certainly be carried out. However, to maximize job promotions, we are sometimes constrained by age, which is no longer young, and educational qualifications that are not yet at the bachelor's degree level. If all these requirements are met, it will certainly facilitate job promotions.”

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be interpreted that job promotions and rotations at the Cepu District Education Coordinator have been implemented and have been able to encourage equitable service delivery. However, the effectiveness of promotions and rotations is still influenced by employee motivation to learn, age factors, and formal educational qualifications. Therefore, improving education and continuous training are important supporting factors so that promotions and job rotations truly have an impact on increasing human resource capacity.

Table 2. Job History Regional Coordinator for Education in Cepu District

No.	Name & Rank	Position History	Notes
1	Sri Rahayu S., S.Pd. Senior Supervisor (Pembina Tk. I), IV/b	1. Teacher (1986) 2. School Supervisor (2012) 3. Regional Coordinator / Korwil (2024)	1. Regional Coordinator (Korwil) 2. Supervisory Assistant (Dabin)
2	Aris Munandar, S.Pd., M.Pd. Senior Junior Supervisor (Pembina Utama Muda), IV/c	1. Teacher (1993) 2. School Principal (2012) 3. School Supervisor (2013)	Supervisory Assistant (Dabin) 3
3	Eko Setyo Budi, S.Pd.SD Senior Administrator (Penata Tk. I), III/d	1. Teacher (2009) 2. School Principal (2023) 3. School Supervisor (2025)	Supervisory Assistant (Dabin) 3
4	Sartono, S.Pd. Senior Administrator (Penata Tk. I), III/d	1. Teacher (2009) 2. School Supervisor (2025)	Supervisory Assistant (Dabin) 3
5	Karsono, S.Pd. Junior Administrator (Penata Muda Tk. I), III/b	1. Teacher (2014) 2. Education Administration Staff (2021) 3. Office Administration Staff (2025)	Finance
6	Sugeng Prasetyo, A.Ma. Junior Administrator (Penata Muda), III/a	1. Teacher (2009) 2. Education Administration Staff (2023) 3. Office Administration Staff (2025)	Finance
7	Sinto Junior Administrator (Penata Muda), III/a	1. Security Staff (2009) 2. Education Administration Staff (2013) 3. Office Administration Staff (2015)	Personnel Affairs
8	Masrukin Assistant Administrator (Pengatur Muda Tk. I), II/b	1. Security Staff (2006) 2. Education Administration Staff (2021) 3. Office Administration Staff (2025)	Personnel Affairs
9	Sukiran Assistant Administrator (Pengatur Muda), II/a	1. Security Staff (2007) 2. Education Administration Staff (2023) 3. Office Administration Staff (2025)	1. Attendance 2. Monthly Reports 3. Asset Management

Source: Official Regional Coordinator Document (2025)

4) Mental Development and Work Discipline

Mental coaching and work discipline are fundamental aspects in improving employee performance. This coaching aims to foster a sense of responsibility, work ethic, and discipline among employees in carrying out their duties.

Based on interviews with the Head of the Regional Education Coordinator of Cepu District, mental coaching and work motivation are carried out continuously, both through formal and informal forums:

"We always monitor and provide guidance and motivation to employees regarding their performance in order to improve their mental attitude and performance. Employees who are considered to have poor performance are always motivated to improve their performance so that they can be on par with their colleagues who are considered to have better performance and discipline in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. This is done both in meetings and during informal gatherings. However, sometimes this motivation is not utilized properly, so that on several occasions they ask for help from other colleagues to complete their work."

From the employee" perspective, direct monitoring by superiors has a positive impact on their morale and work discipline:

"Monitoring by superiors of our work can improve our morale and work discipline in completing our tasks. We always consult with them about everything we do and sometimes ask them about the progress of our work. Whenever we encounter difficulties, our colleagues are always willing to help so that the work can be completed."

However, from the perspective of service users, there are still weaknesses in work discipline. This was conveyed by the principal of SDN Gadon:

"The assignment of responsibilities and the mental and disciplinary training of employees in carrying out their duties need attention. Sometimes letters or files are often lost even though they have been collected."

Based on these findings, it can be interpreted that mental coaching and work discipline have been implemented continuously, but the results are not yet fully optimal. Although there has been an improvement in work completion and cooperation among employees, more consistent supervision and coaching are still needed to minimize negligence and increase work responsibility.

5) Performance Evaluation and Assessment

Performance evaluation and assessment are an important part of HR management to ensure that employees work in accordance with targets and service standards. At the Cepu District Education Coordinator, performance evaluations are conducted regularly through monthly work meetings and an e-performance system.

Based on interviews with the Head of the Cepu District Education Coordination Office, performance evaluations aim to increase employee awareness and responsibility:

"Performance evaluations at the Cepu Coordination Office are conducted frequently, both during monthly work meetings and during e-performance assessments. This is intended to make employees responsible and aware of their performance. The implementation of employee performance evaluations in the Regional Coordination Office has been going quite well, although a little slow, but with the evaluation, employee performance is gradually improving."

This opinion is reinforced by one of the office administrators, who said that evaluations make employee performance more focused:

"Evaluations make employee performance more focused and measurable, which is very necessary for increasing human resource capacity in the Cepu Regional Coordination Office. At the Cepu District Education Regional Office, staff development and evaluation are carried out either monthly or informally, which allows us to use evaluation to improve human resource capacity and work performance."

In addition, teachers and service users also said that evaluations have a positive impact on services:

"Evaluations are important. We have provided feedback on the services at the Cepu Regional Office several times, and this will certainly have a positive impact on services, whether small or large. One positive thing we feel is that it is easy to access the information we want from the Cepu District Education Office."

Based on the results of interviews, observations, and documentation, it can be interpreted that performance evaluations and assessments at the Cepu District Education Coordinator have been carried out routinely and consistently. These evaluations contribute to increasing awareness, responsibility, and the quality of employee performance, as well as having a positive impact on the quality of public services.

Table 3. 2024 Work Meeting Schedule

No.	Month	Work Meeting Date
1	January	17 January 2024
2	February	7 February 2024
3	March	5 March 2024
4	April	9 April 2024
5	May	14 May 2024
6	June	5 June 2024
7	July	9 July 2024
8	August	7 August 2024

9	September	12 September 2024
10	October	16 October 2024
11	November	6 November 2024
12	December	11 December 2024

Source: Official archive of the 2024 work meeting schedule (2025)

4. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that human resource capacity development plays a crucial role in improving the quality of public services in the education sector at the Regional Education Coordinator of Cepu District, Blora Regency. Although capacity-building efforts have been implemented through education, training, promotion and job rotation, mental development, work discipline, and performance evaluation, their effectiveness remains limited by disparities in educational qualifications, unequal access to training, variations in employee motivation, age-related constraints, and insufficient welfare support. Additionally, the absence of a structured mentoring and regeneration system hinders the sustainability of human resource development. These findings indicate that future improvements in public service quality require more inclusive and equitable capacity-building strategies, stronger mentoring mechanisms, continuous performance monitoring, and enhanced employee welfare, while further research is needed to expand empirical evidence through comparative and mixed-method studies.

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